

tray containing $^{32}\text{P}\text{-H}_3\text{PO}_4$ (at a concentration of 0.5 c/ml) in distilled water. The solution level in the tray was high enough to cover most of the seedlings' root area. After 24 hours, the seedlings were transferred to a tray containing only distilled water and then infested with female and male BPH adults that had received no food or water for 3 hours.

The insects were allowed to feed for 24 hours, then were placed in a freezer to kill them. They were placed on a 1.27-cm strip of doublestick cellophane tape affixed to the bottom of a 0.32- × 3.18-cm (1/8 × 1-1/4 in.) aluminum planchet and counted with an Aloka Model TDC-6 scaler.

The female BPH on Yushin seedlings were the most active feeders as indicated by the number of radioactive counts/minute (Table 1). Feeding was intermediate on the japonica Jinheung and lower on the resistant IR747. Female feeding was always higher than that of the male.

In a more extensive trial, eight varieties, each with six replicate seedlings per tray, were compared. The concentration of ^{32}P was 0.43 μC $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4/\text{ml}$ of water solution. Seedlings were placed in the ^{32}P solution for 24 hours followed by replacement of the ^{32}P solution with plain distilled water. One pair of adult BPH per plant was allowed to feed for 24 hours and then anesthetized with ethyl acetate. The insects were prepared as before and then

Table 1. Radioactive counts^a of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* fed on rice varieties labeled with ^{32}P . Republic of Korea

Variety	Reaction ^b to brown planthopper	Brown planthopper	
		Sex	Counts (no.) ^c
Yushin	S	Female	1898 a
		Male	842 b
Jinheung	S	Female	336 bc
		Male	180 c
IR747	R	Female	168 c
		Male	17 c

^aBased on av. of 5 replicates corrected for background.

^bR = resistant; S = susceptible.

^cAny two means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

Table 2. Counts^a of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* on rice varieties labeled with ^{32}P . Republic of Korea.

Variety	Reaction to BPH ^b	Radioactive counts/minute		Count ratio	Relative count of females (%)
		Females	Males		
Tongil	S	19,765	3,129	6.32	100.0
Yushin	S	14,214	2,056	6.91	71.9
Milyang 30	MR-R	4,364	292	14.95	22.1
Jinheung	S	4,321	620	6.97	21.9
IR747	R	1,394	172	8.10	7.1
ASD 7	R	1,188	306	3.88	6.0
Suweon 264	MS	1,098	408	2.69	5.6
Mudgo	R	789	934	0.84	4.0

^aAv. of 6 counts/sex per variety, corrected for background.

^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

counted with a Tracerlab Versamatic 11 Scaler.

The highest counts were for BPH that fed on Tongil and Yushin varieties (Table 2). These two varieties, which now grow on about 60% of Korea's rice land, were injured somewhat during the 1975 BPH epidemic. But because they matured earlier, they suffered less injury than the local japonica. The resistance of the newer selections Milyang 30 and Suweon 264 is promising. Again differences in the counts of female and male insects, expressed as a ratio, were significant. Only on Mudgo, which is resistant to BPH biotype 1, were counts

of males higher than counts of females, but the difference was not significant. (The presence of BPH biotypes has not been observed in Korea.) Assuming a relative preference of 100% for Tongil, the relative counts of females matched the results of conventional varietal screening tests perfectly (Table 2).

Additional trials include other leafhopper and planthopper species. Radiotracers not only facilitate resistance screening but could conceivably be used in the analysis of biotypes and in tests requiring quantitative assessment of insect activity.

Field reaction of rices to the brown planthopper and ragged stunt virus

E. A. Heinrichs, entomologist, and V. Viajante, research assistant, International Rice Research Institute

The incidence of ragged stunt virus, transmitted by the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, has been high at IRRI since late 1976. In 1977, three experiments were conducted to determine the field resistance of the IR varieties, breeding lines, and entries in the International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) to BPH and ragged stunt.

In all experiments, the BPH population was promoted by spraying susceptible border plants surrounding the test entries with synthetic pyrethroids, cypermethrin, or

decamethrin (see article in this issue for details).

The following IR rices evaluated in the field at IRRI were resistant to BPH and had low ragged stunt incidence (less than 17% of hills infested): IR32, IR2863-38-1-2, IR4432-52-6-4, IR4432-103-6-4, IR4570-83-3-3-2, and IR5853-118-3. IR29 had 76% and 100% of hills infested in two experiments. IR32 is resistant and IR29 is susceptible to biotype 2 of the BPH, currently considered the predominant biotype at IRRI. In greenhouse tests these breeding lines are resistant to the three biotypes of BPH. All have CR94-13 (PTB18/PTB21//IR8) as a common resistant parent, except IR4570-83-3-3-2 which has PTB18 in its ancestry.

Evaluation of the 1977 IRBPHN indicated that varieties such as PTB19,

Evaluation of selected third International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (1977) entries to brown planthopper and ragged stunt. IRRI, wet season, 1977.

Variety ^a	BPH count/hill ^b 70 DT	Ragged stunt (%)	BPH damage rating ^c 80 DT	Resistance to BPH biotypes ^d in greenhouse		
				1	2	3
B2360-11-3-2-3	118	100	5	R	S	R
Chianung sen yu 19	279	90	7	R	S	S
CR94-13	60	79	3	R	R	S
CR179-1-717	56	72	5	R	R	S
IR2307-72-2-2-1	65	75	7	R	S	R
Taichung sen yu 204	57	98	7	R	S	S
Triveni	36	61	5	S	S	S
ARC 6650	37	96	7	R	R	S
Babawee	9	29	1	R	R	R
Balamawee	33	8	1	R	R	R
Gangala	29	28	1	R	R	R
Heendoramawee	15	58	1	R	R	S
Hondarawala	30	34	1	R	R	R
Lekam Samba	100	13	1	R	R	R
Muthumanikam	160	23	1	R	R	R
PTB19	56	7	1	R	R	R
PTB21	38	0	1	R	R	R
PTB33	48	0	1	R	R	R
Rathu Heenati	37	19	1	R	R	R
Sinna Sivappu	14	4	1	R	R	R
Sudu Hondarawala	44	56	1	R	R	R
Thirissa	16	59	1	R	R	R
Suduru Samba	69	31	1	R	R	R
ASD 7	58	61	5	R	R	S
Mudgo	238	76	7	R	S	R
TN1	121	100	9	S	S	S

^a Field study replicated four times. Four border rows of IR19173-17 planted at ends of test entry rows and two rows planted between each test entry. Plot size of test entries was 1 m² and consisted of four rows of four plants each, spaced at 25 × 25 cm.

^b Collected with a D-Vac suction machine. All BPH adults at 30 days after transplanting (DT) and mostly nymphs at 70 DT.

^c Based on the Standard Evaluation System for rice: 1 = no damage; 9 = plants dead.

^d R = resistant; S = susceptible.

PTB21, PTB33, and Sinna Sivappu, all of which have high resistance to the three biotypes in greenhouse studies, had the lowest BPH damage rating and the least ragged stunt (see table). Because of the small plots and high BPH populations in the susceptible border rows, hoppers were abundant even on resistant varieties at 70 days after transplanting. Varieties that were susceptible to biotype 2 generally had a high incidence of ragged stunt. It was not determined whether resistance to the vector or resistance to the disease, or both, caused the low ragged stunt incidence in certain varieties.

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN Duplicate prints of photos and illustrations are available to media on request from the Office of Information Services, IRRI. Persons who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.

Allelic relationships among four genes for BP13 resistance

Ryoichi Ikeda and Chukichi Kaneda, Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Konosu, Saitama, Japan

Three years after the rice variety IR26 was released, its resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) broke down. Several breeding strategies for the control of BPH have since been suggested. At the international symposium on BPH held at IRRI in 1977, four strategies were proposed: 1) sequential release, 2) pyramiding the major genes, 3) multiline varieties, and 4) horizontal resistance.

In combining two or more resistance

genes, the allelic relationships among the four known resistance genes must be determined. We made crosses among the four resistant cultivars Mudgo, ASD7, Rathu Heenati, and Babawee, representing *Bph 1*, *bph 2*, *Bph 3*, and *bph 4* genes, respectively. Then the F₂ and B₁F₁ populations from each cross were analyzed by the bulk seedling test, using BPH biotype 1.

Results indicate that 1) *bph 2*, as well as *Bph 1*, segregates independently of both *Bph 3* and *bph 4*; 2) not only *Bph 1* and *bph 2* are either allelic or closely linked, *Bph 3* and *bph 4* are also closely linked.

According to the results, we may be able to combine *Bph 1* with *Bph 3*, *Bph 1*

with *bph 4*, *bph 2* with *Bph 3*, or *bph 2* with *bph 4* in a cultivar. On the other hand, it may be difficult to combine *Bph 1* with *bph 2*, or *Bph 3* with *bph 4*.

According to Lakshiminarayana and Khush (1977), PTB 21 has one dominant and one recessive gene, and one of them is either *Bph 1* or *bph 2*.

To identify the other gene of PTB 21, the cultivar was crossed with Rathu Heenati and Babawee. No susceptible plants were observed in the F₂ populations of either cross. It appears that the other gene of PTB 21 is either *Bph 3* or *bph 4*. It may be concluded that the resistance in PTB 21 is controlled by either *Bph 1* and *bph 4*, or *bph 2* and *Bph 3* gene pairs.